

CYBERLENINKA

BASE

OpenAIRE

Google Scholar

SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Zokirova Barchinoy Makhmud qizi

THE STRUCTURAL ASPECT OF PROHIBITION IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK PAREMIOLOGICAL UNITS

DRJI

Universal
Impact Factor

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

2023-2024

zenodo

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

ADVANCED SCIENCE INDEX